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Open Science Guidebook: Open Science Communities

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Grassroots campaigns led by pioneering scholars are perceived to have a central role in the transition to Open Science, and particularly regarding the normalization of open research practices. Bottom-up networks promoting Open Science, also known as Open Science communities, are a single increasingly visible manifestation of this type of grassroots activity. OS Communities bring together researchers from across disciplines and different career stages for the purpose of facilitating adoption and mainstreaming of OS practices. Over the last few years, a multitude of Open Science communities with diverse emphases and approaches have emerged worldwide. Despite their differing aims and scopes, the OS communities are all jointly working towards integrating open scholarship into research community by advancing research transparency, reproducibility, and integrity through research practice reform.

1. WHAT

In recent years, OS has become a recognized course of action in academic environments. However, the actual adoption of Open Science practices often lags behind. While some practices, such as OA publishing, have reached levels of adoption that allow them to be viewed as to have become the standard way of producing scientific knowledge, others are not close to being mainstream. One of the main barriers on the way to a wider adoption of OS practices has been recognized to be the academic culture itself. A shift towards a culture more favorable of Open Science is an interplay between multiple factors, including provision of necessary and easy-to-use infrastructure to make the OS practices feasible in the first place, normalization of OS practices, introduction of incentives for researchers to adopt OS practices, and imposition of policies to further consolidate their application.

Open Science communities are bottom-up learning and advocacy groups for researchers at different career stages and disciplines. They gather researchers together to discuss experiences and concerns about the application of diverse OS practices. In addition, they actively seek to engage in dialogue with stakeholders, such as institutions, funders and publishers, to promote more transparent research practices and find solutions to overcome obstacles hindering their widespread adoption. By breaking the boundaries of academic fields and geographical locations, OS communities contribute to making the discussion of Open Science more diverse and representative of the varied needs of academics.

While OS communities are typically characterized by their researcher-led operations model and local embeddedness in a specific institution or area, they are often closely interconnected to their counterparts in other countries forming vast international networks of similarly oriented communities providing added leverage in their efforts to institutionalize Open Science through shaping institutional OS policies and dialogue with external stakeholders. International umbrella organizations offer pre-existing networks for new communities to tap into, and on-boarding and practical support in setting up one's own institution- or city-based node.

2. WHY

Being inclusive and easily approachable communities offering a low entry point into Open Science and increasing the visibility of OS practices in their local setting, OS communities have potential to act as important drivers of the cultural shift especially in terms of normalization of Open Science practices. Overall, OS communities enable advancement of knowledge, facilitate communication and provide support for effective adoption and mainstreaming of OS practices among scholars.

OS communities may also serve as a fertile ground for the emergence of impactful OS initiatives, and multiple notable examples of such cases already exist. While holding on to their grassroots identity and relative independence from their respective institutions, many OS communities actively pursue meaningful interactions with a variety of stakeholders to advance the common cause of promoting more transparent, inclusive and reliable high-quality research.

From a researcher's perspective, OS communities provide a platform for peers to interact, get inspired and learn from one another, to acquire skills and receive guidance on OS practices that one may already be familiar with and also on practices that may not yet be applied commonly in all disciplines. Moreover, sharing experiences about OS practices may reveal that sometimes researchers from different disciplines have a lot of things in common, even more than one might have initially assumed.

3. HOW

For those who are interested in participating in OS community activities or establishing a local OS community, it would be useful to note the following points:

- OS communities are open especially to researchers in academia, but also to e.g., students, research managers and administrators, funders, publishers and citizens.
- OS communities focus on e.g., organizing, promoting, and facilitating events and workshops for researchers to learn about and discuss open science practices, share their expertise, and build professional networks.
- Some of the prominent examples of international umbrella organizations of OS communities are International Network of Open Science & Scholarship Communities (INOSC), Reproducibility Network (RN) and Open Knowledge Foundation (OSF).
- The activity and success of an OS community depend on the contributions of its members.
- When establishing a new local OS community, it is not necessary to reinvent the wheel because there are many existing bottom-up OS communities worldwide that have navigated through different obstacles and are willing to share their knowledge and experience.

RESOURCES AND FURTHER READING

- International Network of Open Science & Scholarship Communities (INOSC):
 - <https://osc-international.com/>
- Reproducibility Network (RN) country nodes:
 - DE: <https://reproducibilitynetwork.de/>
 - FI: <https://www.finnish-rn.org/>
 - IT: <https://www.itrn.org/>
 - PT: <https://www.ptn.pt/>
- Open Knowledge Foundation
 - <https://okfn.org/>
- Berkeley Initiative for Transparency in the Social Sciences:
 - <https://www.bitss.org/>
- Armeni, K. *et al.* (2021) 'Towards wide-scale adoption of open science practices: The role of open science communities', *Science and Public Policy*, 48(5), pp. 605–611. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scab039>.
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